

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: CORE Oceanic variables

ag - agregation for the highest-frequency output: i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval (in model); c: cumulative over sampling period

Version: 2024-06-25

Output variable	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency			Priority	Comments
					mon	day	1hr		
thetao	degC	a	Sea Water Potential Temperature	sea_water_potential_temperature	x			CORE	3D, potential temperature
so	0.001	a	Sea Water Salinity	sea_water_salinity	x			CORE	3D, practical salinity
uo	m/s	a	Sea Water X Velocity	sea_water_x_velocity	x			CORE	3D, positive: east
vo	m/s	a	Sea Water Y Velocity	sea_water_y_velocity	x			CORE	3D, positive: north
zos	m	a	Sea Surface Height Above Geoid	sea_surface_height_above_geoid	x	x		CORE	2D, the GCM zostoga variable should be added in the monthly file
tos	degC	a	Sea Surface Temperature	sea_surface_temperature	x	x		CORE	2D
sos	0.001	a	Sea Surface Salinity	sea_surface_salinity	x	x		CORE	2D
mlotst	m	a	Ocean Mixed Layer Thickness Defined by Sigma T	ocean_mixed_layer_thickness_defined_by_sigma_t	x	x		CORE	2D, positive: down, Med-CORDEX: Use a criteria of 0.011 or 0.01 kg/m³ with a 10m-depth reference
areacello	m²		Grid-Cell Area for Ocean Variables	cell_area			fx	CORE	Horizontal area of ocean grid cells
deptho	m		Sea Floor Depth Below Geoid	sea_floor_depth_below_geoid			fx	CORE	
sftof	%		Sea Area Percentage	sea_area_fraction			fx	CORE	Percentage of horizontal area occupied by ocean.
thkcello	m		Ocean Model Cell Thickness	cell_thickness			fx	CORE	
volcello	m³		Ocean Grid-Cell Volume	ocean_volume			fx	CORE	

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 1 Oceanic variables

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output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency			Priority	Comments
					mon	day	1hr		
thetao	degC	a	Sea Water Potential Temperature	sea_water_potential_temperature		x		TIER1	3D, potential temperature
wo	m/s	a	Sea Water Upward Velocity	sea_water_z_velocity	x			TIER1	3D, positive: up
rhof	kg/m3	a	Sea Water Potential Density	sea_water_potential_density	x			TIER1	3D, sigma0
hfds	W/m ²	a	Downward Heat Flux at the Sea Water Surface	surface_downward_heat_flux_in_sea_water	x	x		TIER1	2D, positive: down, This is the net flux of heat entering the liquid water column through its upper surface (excluding any "flux adjustment" ?)
hfcorr	W/m ²	a	Heat Flux Correction	heat_flux_correction	x	x		TIER1	2D, positive: down, if this does not vary from one year to the next, report only a single year. Positive indicates correction adds heat to ocean
rsnlds	W/m ²	a	Net Downward Shortwave Radiation at Sea Water Surface	net_downward_shortwave_flux_at_sea_water_surface	x	x		TIER1	2D, positive: down, This is the flux into the surface of liquid sea water only. This excludes shortwave flux absorbed by sea ice, but include any light that passes through the ice and is absorbed by the ocean
tauvo	N/m ²	a	Surface Downward X Stress	surface_downward_x_stress	x	x		TIER1	2D, positive: east
tauvy	N/m ²	a	Surface Downward Y Stress	surface_downward_y_stress	x	x		TIER1	2D, positive: north
uofs	m/s	a	Surface X Velocity	surface_x_velocity		x		TIER1	2D, positive east
vofs	m/s	a	Surface Y Velocity	surface_y_velocity		x		TIER1	2D, positive north
wfo	kg/m ³ s	a	Water Flux into Sea Water	water_flux_into_sea_water	x	x		TIER1	2D, positive: down, P+R-E+corrections
friver	kg/m ³ s	a	Water Flux into Sea Water from Rivers	water_flux_into_sea_water_from_rivers	x	x		TIER1	2D, positive: down, computed as the river flux of water into the ocean divided by the area of the ocean portion of the grid cell.
wfonocorr	kg/m ³ s	a	Water Flux into Sea Water Without Flux Correction	water_flux_into_sea_water_without_flux_correction	x	x		TIER1	2D, positive: down, including runoff, without corrections
gibfx	m3/s	a	Water Transport through Gibraltar Strait	gibraltar_water_flux_net	x	x		TIER1	1D, positive: east, net water transport; formally this means the integral along the line of the normal, Med-CORDEX: Gibraltar Strait (5.6W)
gibfxin	m3/s	a	Eastward Water Transport through Gibraltar Strait	gibraltar_water_flux_in	x	x		TIER1	1D, positive: east, inflow water transport; x_velocity > 0, Med-CORDEX: Gibraltar Strait (5.6W)
gibfs	kg/s	a	Net Salt Transport through Gibraltar Strait	gibraltar_salt_flux_net	x	x		TIER1	1D, positive: east, net salt transport, Med-CORDEX: Gibraltar Strait (5.6W)
gibfsin	kg/s	a	Eastward Salt Transport through Gibraltar Strait	gibraltar_salt_flux_in	x	x		TIER1	1D, positive: east, inflow salt transport, Med-CORDEX: Gibraltar Strait (5.6W)
gibhf	W/m ²	a	Net Heat Transport through Gibraltar Strait	gibraltar_heat_flux_net	x	x		TIER1	1D, positive: east, net heat transport, Med-CORDEX: Gibraltar Strait (5.6W)
gibhfin	W/m ²	a	Eastward Heat Transport through Gibraltar Strait	gibraltar_heat_flux_in	x	x		TIER1	1D, positive: east, inflow heat transport, Med-CORDEX: Gibraltar Strait (5.6W)

CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 2 Oceanic variables

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output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency			Priority	Comments
					mon	day	1hr		
so	0.001	a	Sea Water Salinity	sea_water_salinity		x		TIER2	3D, practical salinity, useful for BGC model forcing
uo	m/s	a	Sea Water X Velocity	sea_water_x_velocity		x		TIER2	3D, positive: east, useful for BGC model forcing
vo	m/s	a	Sea Water Y Velocity	sea_water_y_velocity		x		TIER2	3D, positive: north, useful for BGC model forcing
wo	m/s	a	Sea Water Upward Velocity	sea_water_z_velocity		x		TIER2	3D, positive: up, useful for BGC model forcing
rhop	kg/m3	a	Sea Water Potential Density	sea_water_potential_density		x		TIER2	3D, sigma0
difvho	m2/s	a	Vertical Eddy Diffusivity	ocean_vertical_heat_diffusivity		x		TIER2	3D, useful for BGC model forcing
tos	degC	a	Sea Surface Temperature	sea_surface_temperature			x	TIER2	2D
tob	degC	a	Sea Water Potential Temperature at Sea Floor	sea_water_potential_temperature_at_sea_floor	x			TIER2	2D